

Lessons educators could learn from Thomas Kuhn's the structure of scientific revolutions

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The purpose of this article was to explore some valuable lessons and experiences that have relevance for the field of education and its professionals. Thus, a critical analysis and reflection is made on some selected issues that were addressed in Thomas Kuhn's book entitled *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Based on these analyses and reflections, the lessons that need to be considered by educators are discussed at length. In this article, we argue that, the book entitled *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* has at least four valuable implications for educators. These are; the need to revisit the current challenges of educational research, the need to strive for paradigm shifts in some educational theories and thoughts, the need to revitalize textbook writing, and the need to reconsider the implications of the two terms, i.e., science and *scientist* in the field of education.

Keywords: educational research, paradigm shift, revolution, science, scientific revolution, textbook

Education is an interdisciplinary field of study. For this reason, it borrows knowledge and experiences from different disciplines, as they are vital to deepen its community's understanding on the multifaceted issues of education. The fields of Philosophy, Psychology, Sociology and History are good examples in this regard. It is based on this premise that, the task of writing this article was initiated. This paper, therefore, aimed to explore some valuable lessons that could be drawn from Thomas Kuhn's landmark book, *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*.

In *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*, Kuhn had judiciously explicated the nature, characteristics, procedures and outcomes of scientific revolutions. In the book, he argued that scientific research and thought are defined by "paradigms," or conceptual world-views that consist of formal theories, classic experiments, and trusted methods. For many scholars (e.g., Price, 1963; Bohm, 1964) Kuhn's *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*, is probably the most important contribution to the historiography of science.

Many believe that *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* has revolutionized the history and philosophy of science, and his concept of paradigm shift was extended to such disciplines as political science, economics, sociology, and business management. These days, the book is used as one of the textbooks of various PhD programs in many universities. For instance, in Bahir Dar University, Ethiopia, it is mandatory to all new entrants of PhD programs as a studentship to devote some weeks for reading, reviewing and reflecting on this book before starting other courses.

This paper, therefore, attempts to indicate the implications and applications of some of Kuhn's ideas to the field of education. For this purpose, attempts are made to briefly familiarize readers with the four major issues deeply explicated in the book. Thus, a brief

critical review on *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* is made underneath each of the four themes selected for reflection. However, readers of this paper need to be reminded that the primary purpose of this article is not to make a book review. Rather, it aims at showing the implications and relevance of the book to the field of education. Hence, the 'review' focuses only on those issues of the book that we believe are important for the purpose of this paper. In order to substantiate the issues under consideration, some related literature and personal experiences and observations are also included. Then, our reflections on the relevance of those issues, and most importantly on the measures that need to be considered by educators, educationists, educational policy makers, educational researchers, textbook writers, and other stakeholders of education are highlighted.

Lessons educators could learn from "the structure of scientific revolutions": Personal perspectives

The structure of Scientific Revolutions, we argue, will undoubtedly compel its readers, particularly those with a background in education, to think over on its versatile implications and relevance to the field of education. Hence, in this part we will briefly indicate and reflect on the implications of some of Kuhn's ideas and their relevance to the education field. Our reflection will focus on the following four themes. These are; the need to revisit the current challenges of educational research, the need to strive for paradigm shifts in some educational theories and thoughts, the need to revitalize textbook writing, and the need to reconsider the implications of the two terms, i.e., *science* and *scientist* in the field of education. Underneath each theme, issues taken from the book and most importantly the positions and suggestions of the author are briefly presented.

The need to revisit educational research

The first important lesson that could be drawn from Kuhn's *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*, we argue, is the one that is related with research. From chapter three to six of the book, Kuhn elaborated, in detail, the essence, nature, characteristics and

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limitations of normal science. The phrase normal science, for Kuhn, simply refers to a research firmly based up on one or more paradigms framed on the basis of past scientific achievements. The author summarized the nature of normal science as a research endeavor that focused on three classes of problems. The three classes of problems that normal science strives are; determination of scientific facts, matching of facts with theory, and articulation of theory. For Kuhn, in the first class of problems researchers focus on and attempt to increase the accuracy and scope of fact gathering. Precision and reliability of methods is very important here. In the next class of problems, he argued, researchers give due consideration for the matching of facts already collected with predictions of the paradigm and theories. At last, in the third class of problems an empirical work that aimed at the articulation of paradigm related theory is undertaken. In so doing, Kuhn showed that normal science is a research that is dominated by the above three problems.

Next to this, Kuhn explained, in Chapter four, the aim and nature of research in normal science. For him, normal science research is a research that aims at articulation of a theory within the existing paradigm and precision of its methods. For Kuhn, research in normal science is a highly pre-determined activity and its concern is like solving a puzzle. It aims at discovering what is known in advance. According to Kuhn, the problems to be investigated in this research should have solutions. Interest and importance are not considered good criteria to choose research problems. The desire to be useful, exploring new territory, finding order, and testing an established knowledge are also not the concerns of a normal science research. As a result, Kuhn argued, "the really pressing problems (e.g., a cure for cancer or the design of a lasting peace), are often not puzzles at all, largely because they may not have any solution" (pp. 36-37). According to Kuhn, assured solutions, rules of acceptable solutions and steps, generalizations, understanding the world, improving precision within a specific paradigm, and empirical details are issues that dominate normal science research.

Kuhn has also explained the major limitation of normal science. The major limitation, he contends, is that it does not aim at novelties of fact (discovery) and novelties of theory (innovation). For Kuhn, though novelty of fact and theory are the causes of paradigm change, these fundamental issues are missed in normal science research. According to Kuhn, discovery begins with the emergence of anomaly, a thing or situation that is different from what is normal or expected. Perceiving anomaly is considered essential for perceiving novelty. Discovery commences with the awareness of anomaly. It then continues with the exploration of the area of anomaly. And it closes only when the paradigm theory has been adjusted so that the anomalous has become the expected. In short for Kuhn, anomaly is the basis for scientific discoveries and it emerges with difficulties and resistance.

Kuhn's discussion of the normal science research has direct implications on contemporary educational research. Based on the literature reviewed hereunder and our personal experience and observations, it is possible to understand that, many of the features of normal science research described by Kuhn also characterize contemporary educational research practices. Hence, at this juncture it seems imperative to briefly look at the status and challenge of educational research, so as to understand how current educational research shares many of the features of normal science research, and most importantly to rethink on the measures that might possibly improve the current research scenario.

Status and challenges of educational research: Many studies (e.g., Belete, 2016; Reese, 2007; Hoban, 2002; Pring, 2000) conducted on the historical development and current state of educational research unanimously indicate that the field of research has been overwhelmed by too many challenges that lead to the preponderance of skepticism and despair on its ability to advance the field of education. For instance, Lagemann (1997) indicated that the history of educational research has been characterized by continuing contests among different groups, especially scholars of education, scholars of non-education disciplines, school administrators, and teachers. For her, for the past 120 years, the above groups and scholars have been debating on questions such as; what educational research is and what should, and who can and should conduct and appraise educational research?

Hoban (2002) by referring to Lagemann, indicated the major problems of education that lead to low level status of educational research. For this scholar, *the isolation of education from university scholarship, the early technical nature of educational research, and lack of a professional community* are the three major problems of educational research. The separation of education from well developed and highly prestigious fields of study (such as Philosophy) was soon followed by strong criticisms, and university academies began to consider the new field (educational science) as a low status field. Besides, this isolation of the field from the recognized disciplines is reported to be inhibitive to develop systematic procedures to ensure quality research (Hoban, 2002).

In the same fashion, many scholars indicate that contemporary educational research practice in many countries is besieged with too many challenges. In this regard, Farrington (2003) reported that "questionable quality" has been one major challenge. According to this scholar, weak design methodology, poor reliability of measures, mismatch of research questions and objectives, shallow depth of analysis, lack of scientific rigor, and weakness in reporting it are just some of the issues that daunt the quality of educational research. While discussing the criticisms of contemporary educational research, Pring (2000) mentioned the following four general limitation of educational research. These are; *inability to provide the answers to the questions governments ask, failure to guide professional practice, being fragmented, and being tendentious or politically motivated* (p.2). Likewise, Belete (2016) stated that questionable quality and relevance, gap between educational research and practice, between educational research and policy making, and disjuncture among research, policy and practice are the major challenges of educational research. For him, practitioners' reluctance to use research outputs, and policy makers' lack of interest to use research as evidence base to formulate policies, inappropriate research dissemination model (take it approach) are among the factors that attribute to the low status of educational research currently.

Nowadays, in educational research, inconclusive debate is taking place, particularly among the advocates of positivism, interpretivism, and critical research theory (Cohn, Manion, & Morrison, 2005; Pring, 2000). Due to this, much time has been spent in talking and hearing this paradigmatic debate. Besides, educators in universities with these different research paradigms are confusing their students by deliberately emphasizing one at the expense of the other. This situation, the prevalence of competing research perspectives/paradigms are considered as challenge that are inhibiting educational research to bring the desired progress in education

(Pierre, 2016; Belete, 2016; Cohn, Manion, & Morrison, 2005; Pring, 2000).

Meanwhile, many educators (e.g., Pierre, 2016; Reese, 2007; Pring, 2000; Carr & Kemis, 1986) assert that the predominance of the positivist research paradigm, with much reliance on scientific methods and the quantitative research approach, has been a challenge in educational research. For instance, Pierre (2016) argued that educational research curriculum that emphasized formalized, scientized, pre-existing, and methods-driven research methodologies has become dominant in educational research, and due to this situation, she argues, has stifled the present educational research and continues to stifle it in the future.

From the above discussion, it is not difficult to understand that educational research has been besieged with many challenges. Uninterestingly, this scene remained almost unchanged after the field's travel for more than a century. Due to the challenges indicated above, and many other related reasons, educational research and researchers today are not able to play their roles in advancing the field of education. In this regard, Pring (2000) by referring to Hargreaves, summarize the situation as follows.

... despite the enormous amount of money spent on research and the large number of people who claim to be active researchers, there is not the cumulative body of relevant knowledge which would enable teaching to be (like medicine) a research-based profession (p. 2).

Shulman (1970) also asserted that, research endeavors in education have been undertaken without achieving their purposes. In this regard, the author wrote:

If the object of such research is the development of coherent and workable theories, researchers are nearly as far from that goal today as they are from controlling the weather. If the goal of educational research is significant improvement in the daily functioning of educational programs, I know of little evidence that researchers have made discernible strides in that direction (p.371).

For this educator, "a kind of educational research has been attempted without notable success" (p. 392). The most important reason that this educator considered behind this problem was the predominance of the traditional methods of research (e.g., experimental research) in the field of educational research.

Our professional experience as secondary school teachers, education senior experts and teacher educator at higher learning institutions, for more than twenty years, is also in line with what has been discussed so far. That is, we witnessed that most of the challenges of educational research discussed above are prevalent, for example, in the education system of Ethiopia. The most important challenge that one can easily observe in the education system of Ethiopia is the predominance of the positivist research paradigm and the reluctance of many educators to accept other emerging research paradigms. Put differently, there is much reliance on the quantitative research approach. Due to this, the curriculum of education colleges in the country gives due attention for the training of quantitative research methodology at the expense of other emerging methodologies. Teaching students, both undergraduate and graduate, an independent course on qualitative research methods, is almost in existent in the country's teacher education institutes. This is particularly true for action research. As indicated by Worku (2017) there is a substantial rhetoric-reality gap

concerning the concept and practice of action research. The allocation of too little fund, rigid bureaucratic and financial procedures, reluctance of school teachers to participate in research process, filling in questionnaires with much negligence, and lack of adequate research knowledge, skill and ethics, could also be mentioned challenges of educational research in Ethiopia (Melesse & Kibret, 2014).

Due to the above-mentioned reasons, educational research in Ethiopia is criticized for not helping the improvement of the country's education. To the researchers' best knowledge, no research was reported successful in formulating educational theory that could advance the field of education in the Ethiopian education system. Researches that also aimed at the improvement of classroom/school practices are not worth mentioning (Worku, 2017). It seems due to this general educational research milieu that the country's education system is engulfed by too many problems. Though too many educational problems could be enumerated, low student learning outcome, as confirmed by different national learning assessments, is considered as very critical (World Bank, 2013).

To put it in a nutshell, the above discussion indicates that Kuhn's description of the normal science research has a far-reaching implication and relevance to contemporary educational research. The features of normal science research, described in *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*, also characterize current educational research practices. Many educational researches are reflecting the major features of normal science research. Instead of recognizing many of the educational anomalies as educational crises, we educators tend to view them only as counter instances. Just like normal science researchers, many contemporary educational researchers do not conduct researches that aimed at novelties of fact (discoveries) and novelties of theory (innovations). Also, instead of trying to address the different educational crises, by introducing better educational strategies, we educators are spending most of our research time by emphasizing the rules, procedures, methods, and techniques of the dominant research paradigm, i.e., positivism or post-positivism. Surprisingly, there is a general tendency to appraise the quality and relevance of educational research projects, entirely on the basis of the methods employed and the procedures followed.

On the measures to be taken: Many educators have come up with different strategies to ameliorate the challenges of educational research and most importantly, to improve its present status. For instance, Belete (2016) suggested that strategies such as enhancing quality, rigor, relevance and usability, and improving the research transfer models are vital to reverse the challenges of educational research.

On the other hand, Shulman (1970) on her part emphasized the need to change the training of educational research at universities. She maintained that the solutions to the challenges and difficulties of educational research will not arise from a mere reshuffling of the research designs. For this educator, the approaches employed for training the next generation of educational researchers must change radically. Even more important, the structure of the educational research establishment must be significantly modified to create the necessary conditions for research in education. Quite similarly, Pierre (2016) insists the need to revitalize the curriculum/course of educational research that universities are offering. In this regard, this educator argued that students need to be taught the philosophy and history of different research approaches, before they are taught about methodologies. Besides, she recommends for a reconnection with

forms of inquiry offered by the humanities in an attempt to revitalize inquiry.

Likewise, many educators accentuate on the need to employ different emerging research paradigms and approaches. Advocates of this idea contend that, education by its very nature is a social process, and as a result, all social problems, including educational problems, could not be successfully solved through the application of the scientific methods that are taken from the natural sciences. For this group of educators, educational research needs to rely on methods that are devised by social scientists, if the field is to serve social progress. In this regard, they advocate interpretive research paradigm that gives due attention for qualitative research methods. In line with this, Hoban (2002) asserted that "the growing popularity of qualitative methods and the evolution of different educational perspectives, such as feminist and postmodernist views, could play important roles in addressing some of the challenges, especially the "narrow problematic" nature of the field. The critical research paradigm, which strives for change, improvement and emancipation (Pierre, 2016; Pring, 2000; Carr & Kemis, 1986) is also considered relevant in the field of educational research. For these educators, action research, with its focus on the improvement of classroom/school practice, is considered as a cost-effective and efficient form of inquiry.

In general, educators need to give due attention for the challenges and low status nature of educational research. They need to give attention for anomalies they observe while practicing an existing dominant paradigm. They also need to devote their research time, knowledge, and money towards addressing the crises of educational research. This is because; as implied and understood from *the structure of scientific revolutions*, this task is decisive for the emergence of progress in the field of education, and indeed in society. Hence, these issues need to be revitalized and reconsidered as an important source of deliberation, as failure to do so will significantly jeopardized progress in the field of education.

The need to strive for paradigm shifts in education

The meaning of paradigm, and most importantly the causes, processes and consequences of paradigm shifts are issues that were judiciously discussed in *the structure of scientific revolutions*. Accordingly, Kuhn defined paradigm as any scientific achievement that possesses the following two characteristics. First, a scientific achievement should unprecedentedly attract too many adherents. Second, they should have open-ended problems to be redefined and resolved by practitioners. Hence, a paradigm is any achievement that has attracted many adherents and has open-ended problems to be redefined and resolved by practitioners of a certain group.

Kuhn has also indicated, in chapter seven, that paradigm shift that result from *the invention of new theories* is due to the failure of an existing theory. This failure is considered as a crisis by the scientific community. Kuhn convincingly indicated that, the emergence of a new theory is grounded in the persistent failure of settling problems using the puzzles of normal science. In other words, failure of existing rules is the prelude to a search for new theories. In order to explicate how anomaly leads to crisis and crisis to the emergence of scientific theories, Kuhn explained in detail three examples of crises. The first example was the astronomical crisis. In this example, the failure of *Ptolemaic astronomical theory* to address many issues of astronomy has resulted in astronomical crisis for a long period of time. Ultimately, this crisis had resulted in the emergence of a new

theory of astronomy by Copernicus.

Kuhn has also explained, in chapter eight, how scientists respond to crisis. Accordingly, the following are listed as some responses. These are; losing faith and consider alternatives, not treating anomalies as counter instances, devising numerous articulation and ad hoc modifications of their theory, and leaving the paradigm (those unable to tolerate the crisis). Kuhn also indicated two universal facts about crises. These are: all crises begin with the blurring of a paradigm and the consequent loosening of the rules for normal research, and all crises close in one of the following three ways, i.e., some times normal science handle the crisis-evoking problems, setting aside the problem for next generations, and the emergence of a better new candidate for paradigm.

In short, the author indicated that the existence of anomalies in the normal science could lead to the emergence of crises within an existing paradigm. For Kuhn, it is through the efforts of scientists to solve these crises that a new and better paradigm could replace the old one. And, it is through this process that scientific revolutions could emerge. Thus, the second important lesson that could be learned from *the structure of scientific revolutions* is related with the issue of paradigm shifts.

From Kuhn's discussion of paradigm shift, and the nature and process of a scientific revolution, we believe, educators can have some valuable lessons. For instance, it implies that educators need to be aware of the fact that an educational theory/paradigm that has been accepted by many followers and considered as effective in guiding and solving different educational problems could not always work. An educational thought/theory, after serving the education community, relatively for a long period of time, might become ineffective in addressing all educational issues effectively and efficiently. Hence, this implies that educators need to refrain from blindly adhering to old paradigms as a panacea for all educational problems.

Another related thing that the education community could learn from Kuhn's discussion of paradigm shift is the need to give attention for what Kuhn has called *anomaly*. The existence of anomaly, which refers to a thing, or a situation that is different from what is normal or expected, is a precursor of paradigmatic crises. Hence, in the field of education as well, after a certain period of time, some issues or situations that were not seen during the paradigm's long period may begin to emerge. For instance, over time a certain classroom approach, learning theory or curriculum approach may fail to satisfactorily serve its purpose. So what could be learned from the philosophy of Kuhn is that, educators need to give attention for these issues. In other words, educators, instead of considering them only as counter instances, need to examine the magnitude of their weaknesses, the reasons behind their failure, and most importantly, the possible alternatives that could substitute them. This is because, as Kuhn elaborated, anomalies are things that cause paradigmatic crisis, and it is crisis that might ultimately lead to paradigm shift or scientific revolution.

Thirdly, members of educational communities need to bear in mind that they are responsible to address any crisis that might prevail as a result of the failure of an old paradigm. That is, instead of describing and magnifying educational problems, they need to work collaboratively, in search of alternative theories and strategies that could successfully replace the old ones. Through this process, educators can not only meaningfully solve diverse educational

problems and address educational paradigmatic crises, but also, contribute to the emergence of new paradigms; theories and thoughts that could effectively work in the field of education, relatively for a long period of time, and enable educational communities discharge their professional and societal responsibilities. To put succinctly, it is through the educators' efforts to address the limitations of an old paradigm that a new paradigm, better than the previous one, could emerge in the field of education.

Finally, as Kuhn has clearly indicated, educators need to remember the fact that “the proliferation of competing articulations, willingness to try anything, expression of explicit discontent, the recourse to philosophy and debate over fundamentals are the symptoms of transition from normal to extraordinary research” (Kuhn, 1996, p. 91). Unfortunately, some scholars in the field of education consider these issues as unnecessary and signs of crises. For instance, this issue was reflected in one of the seminal works of Joseph Schwab. In his famous work, commonly known as *the Practical I*, Schwab showed that a rise in frequency and intensity of the eristic, contentious, ad hominem debates as one of the six crisis of the curriculum field (Schwab, 1969). Later studies that were conducted on the basis of Schwab's *the Practical* (e.g., Wraga & Hlebowitsh, 2003; Deng, 2012) too echoed this view. However, continuous scholarly conversations and dialogues on the multifaceted issues of the education field need to be considered as positive, as they might finally lead to the emergence of better educational thoughts/paradigms that contribute for the advancement of the field.

Rethinking on textbook writing

Another issue that readers of *the structure of scientific revolutions*, with a background of education, and particularly with curriculum studies, will be interested is Kuhn's discussion about textbooks. In the book, the factors that inhibit new revolutions/paradigms to be visible to the scientific community are discussed. According to Kuhn, one important reason for the invisibility of revolutions is related to textbooks.

Textbooks that emerge after a paradigm shift tend to exaggerate past achievements of science. For Kuhn, textbooks usually tend to make scientific revolutions invisible for their readers. For instance, by deliberately focusing on past achievements of science, textbook writers try to perpetuate old paradigms. Kuhn contends that the historical reconstruction of previous paradigms and theories in scientific textbooks had made the history of science look linear or cumulative.

To mitigate the above-mentioned problem, Kuhn recommends textbook revision in the aftermath of revolutions. For him, at time of textbook revision the significance of the new revolution must be given due consideration. Besides, factors that led to the collapse of previous paradigms should be included.

This position of Kuhn vis-à-vis textbooks is quite consistent with the writings of many contemporary educationists. In these writings, it is indicated that textbooks, instead of advancing education and society, are serving to perpetuate old and traditional practices that affect life in society. For instance, Patrice Slattery, one of the well known post modern curriculum scholars, indicated that;

By ignoring race, gender, sexual identity, and ethnicity . . . , modern curriculum development models have actually contributed to the frustration, anger, and violence that threaten to destroy

civilization (Slattery, 2006, p.186).

From the above words of Slattery, one can understand that improperly designed and utilized curriculum and curriculum materials, including textbooks, in our times are creating too many problems, and as a result they are threatening the civilization of mankind.

Similarly, educators from the critical curriculum theory contend that in the process of curriculum development and textbook writing, content/knowledge and its selection are neither neutral nor innocence (Apple, 2004). According to these educators, in many education systems, schools, their curricula and textbooks tend to perpetuate the needs and interests of the dominant powers in society. For them, curriculum developers and textbook writers in many countries used to select content and knowledge that benefits only few members of a society, who in practice are those who controls the political, social and economic spheres. Hence, they advice curriculum developers and textbook writers to always be careful in examining and addressing questions such as what knowledge should be incorporated, whose interest can be served in this curriculum, is the curriculum capable of bringing social transformation and others.

Meanwhile, a number of textbook evaluations carried out in different specific educational issues consistently revealed that textbooks used in different settings and educational levels were engulfed by many pitfalls. For instance, textbooks evaluated for gender equality were found to be perpetuating stereotyped views of men and women (Melesse & Habtie, 2018). In many studies, it was reported that textbooks, rather than mitigating the problem of gender inequality were aggravating gender bias among students. They also served as vehicles for enhancing discrimination based on gender. The following words of a female student about her textbooks, for instance, epitomize this contention.

In my textbooks I learned that only men are kings and soldiers, until I read a book in which famous, queens ruled and fought against enemies. In my textbooks I learned that only men are doctors. When I went to a doctor I saw that she was a woman. In my textbook I learned that only men do farming in my country, until, on a train journey I saw women working in the fields. I have learned that I have a lot to learn by seeing (National Council of Educational Research & Training, 2006, p. 1).

Likewise, many textbooks evaluated for multiculturalism, citizenship, democracy, problem solving approach, and others reported that textbooks, in many countries were impediments for the development of many intended pedagogical, educational and societal values (Alemayehu & Assaye, 2014; Alemayeh, 2010).

All of the above ideas confirm the rightness of Kuhn's positions vis-à-vis textbooks. That is, as the science textbooks that Kuhn described, many other textbooks in different fields and countries are found to be inhibitive for the realization of curricular and national educational aims. Hence, it seems logical for educators, especially those responsible for curriculum development and textbook writing to give special attention for textbooks. That is, at time of selection and organization of contents and writing textbooks, they need to give attention for contents/knowledge that could benefit the whole society members, at least the majority, than few members of the society. Besides, they need to emphasize contents and learning experiences that serve for the advancement of the field. Science textbook writers particularly need to give adequate place for new achievements and scientific revolutions. They should also show the limitations and the factors that lead to the collapse of old paradigms.

By so doing, it is possible to make new scientific revolutions visible for students and other concerned bodies of science. And ultimately it is possible to make scientific communities well aware of the multi-faceted issues of the new paradigm.

Are we really educational scientists?

The fourth major lesson that educators could learn from *the structure of scientific revolutions*, is about the issue of progress. As indicated by Kuhn, the ultimate goal of any creative work, including research, should be progress. Likewise, progress must be the outcome of any revolution. For him, the term science is reserved for fields that do progress in noticeable ways. This implies that, a certain field, in order to be considered as a 'science', should make meaningful progress from time to time.

The above position of Kuhn has direct implication for different disciplines and their professionals who consider their fields of study as science and their graduates as scientists. Now days, it is not uncommon to read about the science and art nature of different disciplines. Many disciplines (e.g., management, political education, anthropology, sociology, humanities, & social studies) unequivocally teach their students that their fields are sciences. Management scientists, political scientists, social scientists, are just some of the titles given for graduates of these fields.

The same story is true in the field of education. As of its inception as a field of study in the late 19th century, there has been 'struggle' to make education scientific (Belete, 2016; Reese, 2007; Hoban, 2002). The struggle to make education a science, according to Hoban (2002), was fought between two groups with different views on the nature of education. The first group was led by John Dewey (a Philosopher) while the second by Edward Thorndike (a Psychologist with much interest in the application of the scientific method to the newly emerging field of education). In that debate, Dewey asserted that education should be based on philosophy and that psychology should remain a branch of philosophy. On the other hand, Thorndike favored the science nature of education. Eventually, he separated psychology from philosophy and established a new field called 'educational psychology' (Reese, 2007; Hoban, 2002).

In a nutshell, after the long debate on the philosophical and scientific nature of education, those who advocate the latter, led by Thorndike, were able to influence the field by deemphasizing the philosophical aspect and by emphasizing the scientific aspect of the field (Reese, 2007).

Due to this historical reason, education today is considered as science. While teaching courses on education, pedagogy, teaching, educational management, and educational research, it is customary to explain that all these disciplines are both science and art. Besides, in the field of education, teachers and graduates of different disciplines are not hesitant to use the suffix 'scientist' in describing themselves.

However, on the basis of Kuhn's notion of science and scientist discussed earlier, it might not be convincing to consider a certain discipline as a science, and its graduates as scientists, if the field of study and their professionals are not making adequate progress. Unfortunately, critical analysis on the origin and development of the field of education and its sub-fields clearly indicate that, the progress achieved in the field is generally scanty and too slow (Reese, 2007). Most of the educational thoughts/theories, that dominant contemporary educational policies and practices are those that were

"invented" at the formative period of the discipline, i.e., the beginning of the 20th century. The predominance of the behavioral view of learning, the positivist research paradigm, the social efficiency theory, and the scientific-technical view of curriculum in the school systems of many countries epitomize this contention.

The names of educators/contributors that frequently appear in the literature of different sub-disciplines of education (e.g., Thorndike, Taylor, Tyler, Bobbitt, Skinner, Dewey, Freud) are those who lived many years ago. Put differently, instead of introducing alternative educational theories and principles that are compatible with the current social, economic, political, and intellectual realities of societies, there is high reliance on past educational theories and theorists. Many contemporary educators consider past educational thoughts as the alpha and omega of their education systems. In many countries, especially in the least developed ones, the attempt to innovate educational theories and practices is almost unknown. Besides, there is reluctance, among many educators, to consider some of the emerging educational thoughts as relevant and appropriate.

Based on the above-mentioned issues, it can be understood that the field of education and its professionals are not making adequate progress. The effort of contemporary educators to advance their field of study cannot be considered as sufficient. Undoubtedly, it is due to the preponderance of this unsatisfactory general educational environment that many contemporary educational systems are besieged with lots of challenges. It is also, due to the failure of national educational systems to reverse these educational problems that the planet is engulfed by too many ever-growing social, economic, political, and environmental problems.

So what could be concluded at this juncture is that, in this frustrating educational milieu, the terms *science* and *scientist* in the field of education need to be used judiciously. Besides, members of educational communities need to ask the question, *is our field really a science and are we scientists?* They need also to ask themselves questions such as; is really education, pedagogy, educational management, teaching, and other areas sciences? If so, what progress is achieved in our field? Is the progress in our field adequate? By so doing, professionals should always aim at seeking alternative educational ideas and practices, if their field of study is to be recognized as science, if they are to be accepted as scientists, and ultimately if their field is to demonstrate tangible progress. In a nutshell, from Kuhn's discussion of progress and the nature of science, educators need to remember the fact that any field, be it a natural science, a social science, humanities, education, etc. cannot be considered as science if it fails to bring progress.

Conclusion

This article has tried to explore some lessons that the education community could learn from Thomas Kuhn's seminal work, *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Though, *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions* was written some 55 years ago, we argued, it is still valuable in sharing many useful scientific experiences for diverse disciplines, including the field of education.

The Structure of Scientific Revolutions, it was argued, has some practical implications vis-à-vis the current challenges of the education field. A thorough analysis of the book implies that some challenges that Kuhn had identified many years ago in the field of educational sciences are also challenges of the contemporary education field. This is particularly true in relation to research

practice, the validity of long-lived educational thoughts, the tradition of textbook writing and the adequacy of progress made in the field.

Hence, we conclude that, though many additional lessons could be drawn from the book, the education community could obtain at least four lessons that in turn will lead to better educational research practice, the emergence of better educational paradigms, the amelioration of textbook writing pitfalls, and the consolidation of efforts to bring visible progress in the field so that the use of the two terms, i.e., *science* and *scientist* in the field of education can become convincing and acceptable.

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